

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

**Simulations of global high-resolution
climate and weather models in production
mode**
Deliverable D1.1

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1. Abstract / publishable summary

The central objective of work package 1 of ESIWACE2 is to develop and run coupled model simulations at a resolution as high as possible and with a throughput rate of at least one simulated year per day (1 SYPD) producing full model output. This throughput would be sufficient to use these simulations for operational weather predictions and potentially also to run the models for a couple of decades, to address scientific questions that are related to climate change. Four model configurations are considered (EC-Earth with OpenIFS coupled to NEMO, the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) coupled to NEMO, the ICON model with both atmosphere and ocean, the DYNAMICO model coupled to NEMO) covering both weather and climate configurations as well as well-established models and models that are currently under development. Furthermore, Ocean-only simulations with the NEMO models are also pushed to high spatial resolution (1/36 degree; ~3 km).

This deliverable will give an overview of the main components and algorithms that are used by the different models and outline challenges for the use of pre-exascale machines for weather and climate simulations at very high resolution. The document also includes scalability plots when running the various models on several supercomputers. Furthermore, the efforts in work package 1 regarding the coupling infrastructure and model in- and output (I/O) will be described.

2. Conclusion & Results

The deliverable is documenting the work on the production mode simulations that has continued as part of work package 1. The models are performing well on the supercomputers of the consortium and three of four models are close to or have already met the throughput rate that was outlined in the proposal at the targeted or higher resolution. However, the porting of the model configurations to heterogeneous hardware, and in particular GPUs, remains a challenging task for the modelling groups, illustrating the importance of the work on Domain Specific Languages (DSLs) in work package 2. There is success for the porting of selected model components for the different modelling teams. While the challenge to process the enormous output data volumes, as investigated by the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) in work package 4 as well as ESIWACE2's support for the DYAMOND model intercomparison, will also be difficult to address, there has been progress to make the model I/O more efficient. Overall, the models are in good shape for the porting to pre-exascale EuroHPC systems in the final year of ESIWACE2. However, there is some concern whether these machines will be available in time.

Please note: This report is on work funded within the project ESIWACE2, which is a direct follow-up of the project ESIWACE that ended in autumn 2019. We have established ESIWACE as a brand for both projects and have not changed the logo. Consequently, in this text, we use ESIWACE to denote the overall activity. Only where it is necessary to address specifically one of the two projects we use "phase 1 of ESIWACE" or "ESIWACE2".

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	Build weather and climate model configurations at the highest possible resolution that are ready for operational use, can leverage pre-exascale compute power, and are candidates for use on exascale machines in the near future
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	Generate synergies between the main model consortia in Europe and push the model resolution that can be used for operational predictions
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	Port production models to the next generation of supercomputers and develop coupling and I/O infrastructure
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	Improve performance and scalability of the leading European models on some of the largest European supercomputers
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	Run production models with full model I/O and improve coupling infrastructure
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	Make the community models ready for use on pre-exascale machines and port the models to several supercomputers while using model configurations that are ready for use by domain scientists
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	Port the models to different supercomputers to understand more about the benefits and challenges on different hardware architecture and make the models fit for use of heterogeneous hardware

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Challenges and recent progress for the use of pre-exascale supercomputers for weather and climate predictions at very high-resolution

Earth System science is currently in the process of a “Digital Revolution” (Bauer et al. 2021). This revolution is needed as a shift to the use of heterogeneous hardware for modern supercomputers makes it necessary to port weather and climate models to various hardware architectures, including accelerators such as Graphical Processing Units. Furthermore, only a couple of percent of the compute power that is available on modern supercomputers (in terms of floating-point operations) can effectively be used by today’s models (Neumann et al. 2019). It is therefore necessary to re-engineer models such that they can be ported to new computer hardware, minimize data movement, and make efficient use of millions of compute processes running in parallel. To improve efficiency of today’s weather and climate models is challenging as the models represent many components of the Earth system and consist of a very large code-base, mainly written in Fortran with MPI/OpenMP parallelisation. To still allow the models to be ported to state-of-the-art hardware, the domain is investigating the use of Domain-Specific Languages (DSLs; as investigated in WP2) that formulate a front end that is covering all important operations and which is exposed to the domain scientists and using a back-end which can be ported to different hardware configurations with no need to change the model code visible to domain scientists. DSL developments go hand-in-hand with developments of scalable algorithms that avoid global communication and allow for the use of unstructured numerical grids (as seen by developments in the ICON and DYNAMICO model, or the Finite Volume Model (IFS-FVM) dynamical core which is in preparation at ECMWF). Furthermore, machine learning is also explored (e.g. in WP2 of ESIWACE2), for example for the emulation of model components to increase efficiency and portability of expensive components of weather and climate models (e.g. Rasp et al. 2018), or for the down-scaling of model output to increase the quality of predictions via a combination of model output and high-resolution information at a local area, including topography fields or observations (e.g. Adewoyin et al. 2021).

Today, global storm-resolving simulations of the atmosphere, which reduce the horizontal grid-spacing to a couple of kilometres, are getting more and more common. It can be expected that an increase to storm-resolving resolution for the atmosphere will allow for significant improvements in model realism as deep convection, topographic gravity waves and surface drag induced by small-scale topography can be represented explicitly within simulations and as satellite data can be assimilated and compared to model output at its native resolution (Neumann et al. 2019). An increase of the grid-spacing in ocean models will allow to resolve a larger fraction of meso-scale eddies and small-scale topography. Global, storm-resolving simulations are getting more-and-more prominent for weather and climate predictions and recent success stories include month-long integrations of a number of models at less than 5 km grid-spacing as part of the DYAMOND project (Stevens et al. 2019). DYAMOND is now in its second phase and includes coupled atmosphere-ocean simulations with resolutions going down to a few km in both components. This intercomparison has also been the starting point for year-long coupled simulations with the ICON model. Within the H2020 project NextGEMS, ICON and IFS will successively be further developed towards full Earth system models at the km-scale, with the goal of 30-year-long integrations within the project. Further high-resolution milestones are a 20-year simulation with 14 km grid-spacing (Kodama et al. 2020) and 1024-member ensemble data assimilation with 3.5-km grid-spacing with the NICAM model (Yashiro et al. 2020), and season-long

simulations with the Integrated Forecasting System with a grid-spacing of 1.45 km (Wedi et al. 2020). It can be expected that global storm-resolving simulations will soon be ready for operational use, for example as part of the Digital Twins of the Destination Earth project.

Model configurations

Table 1 provides a rough overview about the properties of the different model configurations. Further information on the dominant algorithms, status of parallelisation and GPU readiness as well as future plans for model developments are provided in the text below.

Institution	ECMWF	BSC-SMHI	IPSL	DKRZ	NEMO consortium
Model name	IFS	EC-Earth4	IPSL-CM	ICON-ESM	NEMO 4
Atmosphere	IFS CY47R3	OpenIFS CY43R3	DYNAMICO+L MDZ	ICON-A	N/A
Ocean	NEMO3.4	NEMO4	NEMO3.6 or NEMO4	ICON-O	NEMO
Sea Ice	SI3/LIM3	SI3	LIM3 or SI3	Adaptation of the AWI sea ice model	SI3
Land surface	HTESSEL	HTESSEL	ORCHIDEE	JSBACH-Lite	Not applicable
Main purpose	Numerical weather predictions from days to seasons	Climate simulations and research	Climate research	Numerical weather predictions and climate research	Ocean forecasting
Tools for coupling	In house tool	OASIS	OASIS	YAC	Not applicable
Tools for I/O	In house I/O server and FDB software	XIOS	XIOS	CDI_PIO (Parallel asynchronous output)	XIOS, server & multiple files modes
I/O data formats	GRIB for atmosphere, NetCDF for ocean	NetCDF	NetCDF	GRIB and NetCDF	NetCDF
Workflow solution	ecFlow	Shell scripts and Autosubmit	libIGCM (IPSL workflow)	Shell scripts with Slurm	Shell scripts with Slurm (switch to ecFlow is planned)

Building procedure	ecBuild/ CMake	ScriptEngine, FCM	FCM	buildbot tests, automake	Makefile
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Table 1: Summary of model features of the different model configurations

The ECMWF model:

The Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) is based on the spectral transform method where temperature, wind, and surface pressure are represented via spherical harmonics in spectral space but transformed at every timestep to a corresponding grid point space represented on a cubic octahedral reduced Gaussian grid to calculate non-linear terms, the semi-implicit advection, and the physical parameterization schemes. The transformations include both a fast Fourier transformation and a Legendre transformation in both directions (spectral to grid point and grid point to spectral). As time stepping scheme, IFS is based on a semi-implicit semi-Lagrangian scheme. The model is using a Tiedtke scheme for convection with improvements regarding tropical variability and diurnal cycle. The ecRad radiation scheme is currently using a McICA scheme but will soon be replaced by the Triplecloud scheme for operational use. IFS can run both in hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic mode. However, hydrostatic calculations are much cheaper as they avoid additional transformations that are required when running in non-hydrostatic mode. Please see further information on the NEMO model – which is used as ocean component embedded into IFS – below. The production mode simulations are using a TCo2559 grid with a grid-spacing of 4 km for the atmosphere and a ¼ degree grid with 25 km grid-spacing for the ocean.

The use of GPUs has been tested for several model components and in particular for the cloud scheme and the spectral transformations. The spectral transforms can be computed on GPUs in online simulations. Work to port the physical parameterization schemes to GPUs is ongoing. Currently, the parallelization is done via MPI and OpenMP and scalability tests have been performed on a number of machines, including Piz Daint and Summit.

DSL approaches are investigated, in particular for model physics (using a tool called Loki) and the use of a common data framework (ATLAS). IFS-FVM is developed as an alternative dynamical core. IFS-FVM is based on a finite volume scheme with an Arakawa A-grid to avoid the spectral transforms. IFS-FVM is currently ported to Python and rewritten in the Grid-Tools DSL. Machine learning is investigated for the emulation of physical parameterization schemes, pre-conditioning and model post-processing on a research level.

The IFS has the capability to run with either single (32-bit) or double (64-bit) working-precision. Single precision usually delivers an acceleration of the model of around 1.7x compared with double precision, though certain calculations in the Legendre transform must be kept at double precision pending development of a more rounding error-tolerant algorithm. Single precision has been used in the atmospheric component of the IFS for operational weather prediction since May 2021 and is under development in the ocean component NEMO, in collaboration with the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC) and the NEMO Consortium.

The EC-Earth model:

The EC-Earth model has three major components: the atmospheric model OpenIFS cycle 43R3, and the ocean model NEMO 4.0.1, which also includes the sea-ice model SI3. OASIS3 couples the atmospheric and ocean component, while SI3 is included as a module in NEMO.

OpenIFS is the portable version of the IFS meteorological forecasting model and is therefore using the same algorithms as described for the ECMWF model above. NEMO is a state-of-the-art ocean model used for oceanographic research, operational oceanography, seasonal forecasting, and climate research studies that is described in

more detail below. Please see further information on the NEMO model below. Both models are parallelized by domain composition through MPI for distributed memory. OpenIFS supports shared memory parallelization by OpenMP too.

EC-Earth4 is the new version of the model that was developed with the support of ESIWACE. The GPU porting has so far focused on selected model kernels and physics of the atmospheric model, but work is still ongoing, in particular with offloading OpenMP threads to GPUs. There has also been exploratory work to use GPUs to calculate ocean diagnostics.

The resolution of the EC-Earth4 ~10km configuration has ~2M horizontal grid points with 91 vertical levels for the atmospheric component (Tco639L91) and ~13M horizontal points with 75 vertical levels for the oceanic model (ORCA12L75). With the update of the atmospheric component to OpenIFS cycle 43R3, it is possible to use the new and more efficient octahedral reduced grid (Tco639) to substitute the triangular linear one (TL1279) that featured in past versions of this configuration. Compared to standard configurations, the increase in horizontal and vertical resolution and the required reduced time-step leads to an increase in computing resources by two orders of magnitude $O(100)$.

The ICON-ESM:

The ICON coupled model framework for weather and climate applications is based on a hybrid method with finite differences and finite volume approaches. It is discretized on an icosahedron-based triangular grid using an Arakawa C-grid approach. ICON's components are ICON-A, a non-hydrostatic atmosphere model based on developments at Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) and Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), and ICON-O, an ocean model, developed at MPI-M, using the same grid and discretized with a mimetic scheme.

ICON-A can use two different "physics" packages: Sapphire and NWP. ICON-O is based on ocean primitive equations with a free surface, which describe the ocean as a thin fluid layer on a rotating sphere together with the Boussinesq approximation, the hydrostatic approximation and the traditional approximation that neglects the horizontal components of the vorticity vector (Korn, Lindarkis 2018).

For performance improvements, the atmosphere model contains an option for using single precision for variables that are presumed to be insensitive to computational accuracy. This aims to speed up code parts strongly limited by memory bandwidth. It mainly affects the dynamical core and the tracer advection of ICON-A (ICON tutorial 2020). A distinction between the dynamical transport on the one hand, and fast and slow physical processes of the atmosphere model on the other hand, justifies the usage of different integration time steps. This allows sub-cycling where computation is done at individual time steps and at every short time step of the model (Giorgetta et al. 2018).

Both models are parallelized by domain composition using MPI for distributed memory. In addition, nearly all loops that iterate over grid cells are parallelized with shared memory using OpenMP (ICON tutorial 2020).

The ICON atmosphere component with the Sapphire physics package is able to run on NVIDIA GPUs using OpenACC. Recent scalability tests of the QUBICC experiment (without output), using the Sapphire physics package, have been performed on the Piz Daint and JUWELS Booster HPC machines. It achieved a performance of 0.66 SYPD on 387 JUWELS Booster NVIDIA nodes, with a spatial resolution of 5km (R2B9 grid). On CPU nodes, the same experiment showed only 0.05 SYPD on 900 nodes of DKRZs Mistral computer (DKRZ report, 2021). Running ICON-A on GPU machines is of interest for many institutes and partners. One is MeteoSwiss: They will change their operational forecast model from COSMO to ICON within the next year. Since it will run on the GPU machine PitzDaint, MeteoSwiss is currently also porting the NWP physics package to GPU nodes via OpenACC. ICON-A has also been submitted by the Swiss

National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS) as a benchmark for the pre-exascale machine LUMI. In order to enable the model to run on LUMI's AMD GPUs, its vendor HPE/Cray announced to support OpenACC for this benchmark. For a more recent version of ICON-A this support might be insufficient. Therefore, as a fallback solution, a tool that is automatically converting OpenACC directives into OpenMP directives will be developed by the University of Stockholm. A successful feasibility study for this tool has been done by MPI-M, DKRZ, CSCS and HP/Cray.

For the ocean component, first GPU porting using OpenACC directives has been done and will be continued within the CLICCS project by MPI-M. The components of the land surface model that are required for coupled simulations can already run on GPUs, using the CLAW DSL (Clement et al. 2018).

Within ESIWACE2, the DSL approach has also been applied successfully for the dynamical core of the atmosphere model. Here the DSL dusk combined with dawn¹, a community compiler toolchain developed within the ESCAPE-2 project, has been used (see the work of ESIWACE2 WP2). Within ICON-O, some parts are available as prototypes employing DSLs, e.g. CDSL with the dawn toolchain resulting from work within the ESCAPE-2 project (Behrens et al., 2019).

Within the next few years, further work on DSL ports of the ICON-A and -O model components is planned in the German WarmWorld project and the ICON-A model component will be ported to a DSL as part of the Suisse Exclaim project.

The IPSL model:

The IPSL climate model is composed of the DYNAMICO-LMDZ atmospheric model and the NEMO oceanic model. The IPSL model uses OASIS3-MCT as coupler between the atmosphere and ocean component, the XIOS input/output server, as well as the libGCM running environment library.

DYNAMICO, as new dynamical core, is based on a mix of explicit finite volume and finite difference methods, using a TRISK scheme to solve the primitive equations and finite volume discretisation to calculate advection. The model is based on a hydrostatic model running on an icosahedral staggered grid (pentagons and hexagons) that is used as Arakawa C-grid. The vertical discretisation is using sigma-pressure levels. The atmosphere dynamics component (DYNAMICO) has already been ported to GPUs and scaled up to 320 Nvidia V100 GPUs for simulations with 25 km grid-spacing. The parallelisation of the atmosphere component is based on MPI/OpenMP parallelisation.

NEMO uses a finite difference discretization scheme in the horizontal and z-coordinates in the vertical direction. The distribution of variables is a three-dimensional Arakawa C-type grid. The parallelisation is based on MPI only parallelisation.

The use of DYNAMICO-LMDZ as atmospheric component and NEMO4 as oceanic component defines the new version of IPSL climate model.

The NEMO model:

NEMO standing for "Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean" is a state-of-the-art modelling framework for research activities and forecasting services. The primitive equation model is adapted to regional and global ocean circulation problems down to kilometric scale. NEMO is using a curvilinear orthogonal grid in the horizontal direction and either full or partial step z-coordinates, s-coordinates, or the mixture of both in the vertical direction. Variables are distributed as a three-dimensional Arakawa C-grid. The parallelisation is based on MPI parallelisation. Model Outputs are performed with XIOS library servers on dedicated cores.

¹ <https://github.com/MeteoSwiss-APN/dawn>

The high-resolution global configuration (1/36°, 2-3 km resolution) developed here uses a UBS 3th order scheme and no explicit diffusion for momentum advection, 4th order FCT scheme and isopycnal diffusion for tracers, a non-linear free surface (vertical variable volume), split-explicit free surface and the ECMWF-bulk formulae. The NEMO model is not yet ported to GPUs but scalable to 50.000 cores for the ORCA36 grid. Developments towards the use of a DSL, tiling, reading with XIOS, increased halo, and changed time stepping schemes are planned.

Production model simulations

The model simulations of this deliverable will produce the model output as stated in Milestone MS1². Table 2 provides a summary of features of the simulations that have been performed for this deliverable. Further information for each model are provided in the text below.

Institution	ECMWF	BSC-SMHI	IPSL	DKRZ	NEMO consortium
Machine	ECMWF's new Atos Sequana XH2000 supercomputer with 7,680 nodes in 4 clusters ³	BSC's MareNostrum 4 ⁴ with 3,056 nodes and 1.1 PFLOP/s	TGCC's SKL Irene (Skylake) ⁵ with 1,656 nodes (80,000 cores) and 6.86 PFLOP/s	DKRZ's Mistral (HLRE-3) ⁶ with 3,300 nodes and 3.14 PFLOP/s	Météo-France new BULL Sequana XH2000 machine with 30,000 cores (also tested on ECMWF's CCA/CCB and at BSC's MareNostrum 4)
Number of nodes used	1,100	350 - 250	418 nodes (20,000 cores)	783	474
Fraction of machine used (KPI1 - 1)	>55% of one of the four clusters of the machine	10% - 7%	25%	24%	21%

² <https://zenodo.org/record/3685818#.YOgKn7ris2x>

³ <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/newsletter/163/computing/hpc2020-ecmwfs-new-high-performance-computing-facility>

⁴ <https://www.bsc.es/marenostrum/marenostrum>

⁵ <http://www-hpc.cea.fr/en/complexe/tgcc-joliotCurie.htm>

⁶ <https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/mistral/configuration>

Peta-scale equivalent used (KPI1 - 2)	Probably >5 ⁷	1.3 - 0.81	1.715	0.745	2.2
SYPD reached	0.95	1.93 - 1.26	1.5 (12 km atmosphere-only)	0.66	0.25
Powerconsumption (if available)	N/A	4.8kM JPSY (Joules per simulated year)	N/A	N/A	N/A
Fraction of computing time spend in different parts of the model (if available)	Physics: 8.3% Radiation: 1.2% Dynamics: 9.3% Semi-Impl.: 1.1% Trans.: 17.0% NEMO: 4.3% WAM: 6.7% I/O: 35.0% Other: 17.1%	N/A	Dynamics (DYNAMICO): 80%, Physics (LMDZ): 20%	N/A	N/A
Size of the output for a single model day	~2 TB	228 GB	N/A (70 GB estimated)	180 GB	Standard (3D daily, 2D hourly) 143 GB; Highfrequency (3D hourly) 2.72 TB

Table 2: Summary of features of the simulations that have been performed for this deliverable

The ECMWF model:

All results documented here used a TCo2559 grid with a grid-spacing of 4 km for the atmosphere and a $\frac{1}{4}$ degree grid with 25 km grid-spacing for the ocean.

On the CRAY XC-40 ECMWF supercomputer, the production mode simulations achieved a throughput of 0.136 SYPD with 180 nodes, 0.247 SYPD with 360 nodes, and 0.356 SYPD with 720 nodes using the model output as specified in MS1 and following the DYAMOND winter protocol⁸. Here, the number of nodes include 18 nodes for the I/O-server for each run. The timings are taken from a 1-day simulation and calculated from the difference between time at step 360 and 0 with a 240s timestep.

On the new Atos BULL Sequana XH2000 supercomputer we performed additional tests with model output as generated for operational weather predictions, including model

⁷ This is a rough estimate based on the assumption that the new system is ~5 times faster when compared to the old system³. Detailed numbers are not available yet.

⁸ <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond-initiative/dyiamond-specific-pages-and-material/dyiamond-2nd-phase-the-winter-experimental-protocol>

restart files every two days. The operational output includes additional fields that are not part of the DYAMOND model output and the slowdown of performance due to I/O is therefore much more significant. We have therefore generated two sets of runs, with and without I/O. For simulations with I/O, we are allocating one node for the I/O server for ten nodes used for the compute. The estimates of the throughput in table 3 are based on the average throughput for 10-day model simulations. Please note that the results were part of the first tests of simulations with IFS on the new supercomputer and that there is still room for improvements for the efficiency of the production mode simulations.

Number of nodes used	Throughput in SYPD with I/O	Throughput in SYPD without I/O
660	0.84	1.15
880	0.95	1.22
1,100	0.95	1.38

Table 3: Throughput of the ECMWF model using TCo2559 grid performing on Atos BULL Sequana XH2000.

The EC-Earth model:

Figure 1: EC-Earth4 scalability expressed in Simulated Years Per Day (EC-Earth3 with 360s ocean timestep and 720s coupling frequency, EC-Earth4 with 240s ocean timestep and 3600s coupling frequency, climate and high-end outclasses as defined in MS1).

The EC-Earth4 ~10 km configuration has been scaled in the MareNostrum4 supercomputer up to 16.8k cores. Two I/O configurations have been tested: CLIM (corresponding to climate studies and model tuning from MS1) and HE (corresponding to the high-end scenario in MS1). In figure 1, their performance is compared with the EC-Earth3 (ECE3) version in the plot above, but the results need to be interpreted carefully, not only because of the different stepping and coupling frequencies, but also because the parametrizations may vary slightly (even if they are very close to each other). In any case, the change of the TL1279 grid for the Tco639, the higher coupling frequency (explained below), the use of XIOS to output OpenIFS diagnostics together with the improvements in NEMO/SI3 communication explain the increased throughput and scalability.

In the EC-Earth4 tests a timestep of 6 minutes has been used for the atmosphere, while the ocean had to be run with a 4-minute timestep (with the ice module (SI3) run every 12 minutes) due to numerical instabilities. Nevertheless, a spin up run is in progress so that it can be increased in the final deployment phase.

Both components are coupled every hour, which is the frequency used by the *runoff_mapper* component (a simple binary that runs on one CPU). This frequency has proved to be stable in production simulations run with the EC-Earth3 version of the configuration (which was not known during its scaling, which was performed with a 12-minute coupling frequency).

XIOS processes were distributed along the model nodes (OpenIFS and NEMO) for the whole EC-Earth4 scaling. Runs on 50 and 100 nodes use two XIOS I/O servers per node, while only one XIOS server is used beyond 100 nodes. It is still unknown whether the high-end outclass speedup can be improved by leveraging additional I/O servers.

Figure 2: Timeline visualization of the MPI communications during part of an EC-Earth4 execution for the Tco639-ORCA12 configuration running on 10 MareNostrum4 nodes. Components are displayed in the order that they are passed to mpirun, not corresponding with their actual physical affinity.

Figure 2 shows a visualization of a trace obtained from an execution of the ~10 km configuration on 10 MareNostrum4 nodes. The trace is cropped at the end of a coupling phase and shows eight NEMO and 6 OpenIFS steps. The frequency of the ice module (SI3) in NEMO can be figured out by the longer section (white and red, representing *MPI_Recv* and *MPI_Isend*) every three model iterations, while a similar behaviour can be observed in the OpenIFS (bottom) with the radiation module (longer step in the middle of the figure). In this run, the NEMO model is waiting for OpenIFS at the end of the coupling phase. This can be mitigated by using load balance tools such as LUCIA that help to deal with these issues. For the executions featuring the scaling exercise, different runs were done at each scale to balance the resources and obtain the best numbers in each case.

The ICON-ESM:

In order to push the production mode of the coupled ICON model to higher spatial resolution, performance with a grid spacing of 10 km (R2B8 grid) has been investigated. The experiment followed the DYAMOND Winter protocol. Mixed-precision mode and the newly developed parallel output method CDI_PIO were used. The coupled model runs on CPU nodes without using a DSL, except for the land surface model.

Figure 3: Scalability of the coupled ICON with 10km spatial resolution (R2B8) and output according to MS1.

Figure 3 shows the results for scalability. The maximum performance achieved is 0.66 simulated years per day (SYPD) at 783 nodes at the compute 2 partition of the DKRZ Mistral machine. Also, a simulation using 1001 Mistral nodes, corresponding to 32% of the machine (KPI1 - 1), has been done. But due to current limitations of CDI_PIO, the performance decreases if more than 800 nodes are used (see discussion in the next section). These simulations have been done on the supercomputer Mistral at DKRZ, which is already six years old. For its successor machine - Levante - a speedup of a factor of 4 is anticipated. Due to the pandemic crisis installation and access to Levante is delayed: So, the simulations reported here could not yet be repeated on this new machine. Taking the assumed speedup into account, the presented production run would show a performance of 2.64 SYPD.

While the work on the coupled ICON model continues, work on the individual components of ICON is also ongoing in preparation for future exascale machines.

To improve the GPU performance of the ICON atmosphere, scalability tests on JUWELS Booster have been performed. As can be seen in figure 4, the QUBICC experiment computed with ICON-A showed good scalability with a performance of 0.66 SYPD on 387 JUWELS Booster NVIDIA nodes (gray dashed line). The spatial resolution was 5 km (R2B9) and no output was written. On CPU nodes, the same experiment achieved only 0.05 SYPD (on 900 nodes) at DKRZs Mistral computer (DKRZ report, 2021).

For the ICON ocean component, the spatial resolution has been increased. The current performance of ICON-O on CPU nodes is 0.14 SYPD for a global mesh with 2.5 km spatial resolution (262 nodes at DKRZs Mistral). An even finer global grid of 1.25 km resolution could be run and showed a performance of 0.05 SYPD on 1192 Mistral CPU nodes and therefore filled 38% of the machine (KPI1 - 1). Its visualization is publicly available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pj3H8kn8gs>.

Figure 4: Scalability of the QUBICC experiment of ICON-A with 5km spatial resolution (R2B9), no output, on various computing systems (DKRZ report, 2021).

The IPSL model:

The new IPSL model is based on DYNAMICO dynamical core which runs on icosahedral grid. We are working on both the ocean-atmosphere coupled model configuration and the increase of resolution of atmosphere-only configuration.

1. Ocean-atmosphere coupled model: a first version of IPSL climate model has been assembled at 200 km horizontal resolution for atmosphere and ocean component (NEMO v3). This new version is a prototype version which is running to validate the results.
2. High resolution atmosphere-only (DYNAMICO-LMDZ) configuration: dynamics-physics simulation has been performed with up to 20,000 computing cores (Intel SKL):
 - 50km (HighResMIP done), 35 SYPD with no I/O
 - 25 km (HighResMIP in progress), 8 SYPD with no I/O
 - 12 km, 1.5 SYPD with no I/O. An investigation is still in progress to further improve the throughput rate

The scalability plot in figure 5 shows that we reach 1.5 SYPD at 12 km horizontal resolution when using ~20,000 cores Intel SKL. At this resolution, we notice that the computing time spent in the dynamical core is larger compared to the time spent in the physics part, see figure 6. This is mainly due to the larger timestep, when using 28 s for the dynamical core and a timestep of 15 min for physics. The next work will consist in:

- improving the behaviour (scalability) of dynamical part in this configuration
- improving the stability of physical part to avoid crashes of the model
- activating DYAMOND outputs

Figure 5: DYNAMICO-LMDZ scalability at 50km, 25km and 12 km horizontal resolution on Intel Skylake CPUs

Figure 6: DYNAMICO (dynamics) and LMDZ (physics) computing parts at 12 km horizontal resolution on Intel Skylake CPUs

The NEMO model:

The NEMO configuration was not included in the Milestone but will produce daily output for three-dimensional (temperature, salinity, velocities, sea ice variables, vertical mixing coefficient) fields and hourly output for two-dimensional fields (sea surface temperature, height, and horizontal velocities). There are plans to increase output frequency of the three-dimensional fields to hourly output soon: it has been tested on the Météo France Bull Sequana XH2000 on a 1-month period.

The global 1/36° configuration (ORCA36) has been run with NEMO 4 OGCM on the MareNostrum 4 supercomputer. The scalability, see figure 7, was tested up to 122,000 cores and it gives good performances up to 50,000 cores, as the size of the MPP sub-domains decreases. After this value, the cost for communication becomes dominant. More than 122,000 cores would be necessary to reach 1 SYPD. NEMO single-precision provides 89% speedup on 768 cores, 47% on 12,300 cores, and 12% on 49,000 cores.

Figure 7: ORCA36 scalability, based on NEMO 4 OGCM (no forcing, no sea-ice, no outputs)

I/O and storage aspects

The ECMWF model:

For the DYAMOND winter simulations that were running the production mode simulations on the Cray supercomputer at ECMWF, we had model output at the following data volume:

	Output per day for a simulation with 4 km grid-spacing	Output per day for a simulation with 9 km grid-spacing
Atmosphere on model levels	208-218 GB	47 GB
Atmosphere surface fields	104 GB	26 GB
Atmosphere on pressure levels	97 GB	25 GB

Wave model	0.137 GB	0.137 GB
Ocean	13 GB	13 GB
Total	~427 GB	~111 GB

When using the operational output on the new Atos supercomputer, we have generated 20 TB of data for a ten-day prediction and an additional 2.9 TB of data for the model restart files.

The EC-Earth model:

At the end of phase 1 of ESiWACE, we have identified the I/O as the main bottleneck of the EC-Earth3 model. In this version, atmosphere I/O was managed by a master IFS processor, with a growing impact when increasing the resolution or the amount of model fields to output. To overcome this issue, we followed the same approach as the NEMO ocean model, using XIOS as I/O server to improve the I/O management. In addition, this development intended to tackle other critical issues: save model outputs in NetCDF format (mandatory for climate analysis) and unify I/O between atmosphere and ocean, simplifying the workflow. The development started for the IFS standalone version and as soon as it was completed, it was used to release a brand-new EC-Earth4 model. As shown in the scalability plot for EC-Earth (Figure 1), results produced are better than expected. EC-Earth4 is currently delivering more than 1 SYPD as throughput and outperforms EC-Earth3.

High-end outclass (3D 3-hourly output, 2D hourly output): 228 GB per simulated day

The ICON-ESM:

Figure 8: Comparison of gained SYPD and timing spend for output for the coupled ICON with 10km spatial resolution (R2B8).

For the production mode simulation of the coupled ICON model, the newly developed parallel output method CDI_PIO was used. As can be seen in the figure 8, for more than 800 nodes the time for writing the output (green line) increases and therefore significantly reduces the throughput (blue line). This seems to be caused by parts of the output method which are not yet multithreaded. Improvements of this bottle neck are still work in progress.

In the frame of the Monsoon project, the CDI_PIO method is currently ported to JUWELS Booster GPU nodes. This work aims to improve the model performance when it runs on hybrid machines. Although, I/O is normally not suited for GPU nodes, in the case where ICON mainly computes on GPUs, it might reduce intra-node communication as well as memory consumption. This work is mainly done by DKRZ and MPI-M and computing time of 6 million core hours was granted at the Forschungszentrum Juelich through a PRACE call.

The IPSL model:

The IPSL model uses XIOS as I/O server. As described above, working versions of the model at 50 km, 25 km and 12 km horizontal resolution are running with no I/O in order to focus on scalability of computing aspects. However, the amount of data to be produced to satisfy DYAMOND request (3-hourly 3D outputs for 8 fields and hourly 2D outputs for ~20 fields) is about 70 GB (estimation) for the 12 km horizontal resolution. Otherwise, within the CMIP6 HighResMIP project, simulations have been performed with 50 km and 25 km grid-spacing producing IOs to be directly published in the ESGF database thanks to the IPSL CMIP6 data workflow based on XIOS. These runs produced 42 TB at 50 km grid spacing and 160 TB at 25 km grid spacing for the entire 65 years of simulation.

The NEMO model:

When running NEMO4 for an ORCA36 grid, the three-dimensional daily output plus the two-dimensional hourly output generates 143 GB model output per simulated day. If scientific applications request 3D hourly outputs for a short period, the model will generate 2.7 TB of data per simulated day.

Coupling with OASIS3-MCT

The OASIS coupler is used for both EC-Earth and the IPSL model. To support the coupling in the high-resolution production simulations, different developments were achieved in the last two years to complement OASIS3-MCT_4.0 functionality, as planned in the “2020 OASIS3-MCT Development Plan”⁹.

Among these, the following ones have been funded by ESIWACE2:

- Upgrade of OASIS3-MCT compiling environment to support most recent compilers (e.g. gfortran10, intel21, pgi20.4); it involved constructive interactions with MCT developers.
- Extension of *oasis_get_intercomm* and *oasis_get_intracomm* API routines; the extension is about setting up an MPI intercomm and intracomm between more than two components; this is needed by XIOS (in a coupled model involving both XIOS and OASIS3-MCT) when it manages ensemble simulations, as is targeted by task 1.1 of WP1 and WP4.
- Support of fractional masks for the global conservation operation CONSERV.
- New options in global CONSERV operation to conserve fields with positive and negative values with average value close to zero.

OASIS3-MCT developers also contributed to the upgrade to OASIS3-MCT_4.0 (released during phase 1 of ESIWACE) in EC-Earth4. In particular, a bug was found and solved when coupling NEMO with missing land processors¹⁰.

A workaround was proposed but it was found through interactions with NEMO developers that the problem was caused by the halo definition in NEMO; this

⁹ https://cerfacs.fr/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/GlobC-TR-164-202011_OASIS3-MCT_development_plan_final.pdf

¹⁰ see the discussion on the forum

<https://portal.enes.org/oasis/faq-forum/oasis3-forum/debug/557438564>

problem is now solved in NEMO and the recommendation is to use NEMO sources with a version more recent than 4.0.3.

The parallelization of the generation of remapping weights in OASIS3-MCT (funded under phase 1 of ESIWACE) has improved the time required to couple new configurations together. In the case of EC-Earth4 Tco639-ORCA12, all the remapping weights can be generated in a few hours by running OASIS with OpenMP and by creating every different weight in a separate process and in a concurrent manner.

Future work

The ECMWF model:

In the next year, ECMWF will continue the work on GPU portability (in particular regarding the physical parameterization schemes using Loki) and port the production model simulations to the EuroHPC pre-exascale machines as they become available with a particular focus on Lumi and Leonardo. The developments will align well with the preparation of the Digital Twins of the DestinE projects as well as the high-resolution long-term simulations of the NextGEMS project. The single precision version of NEMO will also be used for scalability tests for the production model simulations in the future.

The EC-Earth model:

In the last year of ESIWACE2, BSC and SMHI will continue to work on EC-Earth4. Beside the mandatory task to port the model to a pre-exascale machine, there is room to improve the current performance of the model. BSC will perform a complete profiling analysis of the VHR configuration and if possible, enable to run several years with the mixed-precision version of the ocean, to evaluate the performance gain in a coupled climate simulation. SMHI is engaged in continuous consolidating and releasing the production mode version for end users and in the porting and testing on pre-exascale machines.

The ICON-ESM:

MPI-M and DKRZ will continue to work on GPU portability and port the ICON model to the EuroHPC pre-exascale machines as they become available. Here the focus currently lies on Lumi. As required for KPI 1, a coupled production mode simulation of ICON will be performed at Lumi or Leonardo.

For the I/O, DKRZ will investigate the bottleneck in the CDI_PIO method. Besides the multithreading problem, possible inter-node communication reduction by a better process placement will be tackled.

Another topic of increasing interest is online post processing during production runs (remapping, time means and averages) employing the YAC coupling framework. This idea is investigated by DKRZ and MPI-M.

The IPSL model:

For the fourth year of the project, it is planned to both improve computing performance of atmosphere-only (DYNAMICO-LMDZ) configuration to reach > 1.5 SYPD and to increase the resolution of ocean and atmospheric components in IPSL coupled model. An intermediate working version of the coupled ocean-atmosphere (DYNAMICO-LMDZ-NEMO4 with OASIS) configuration will be configured at 25 km resolution for atmosphere and ocean. The final version of the IPSL coupled model will be running at 12 km resolution for atmosphere and 8 km for the ocean running with the required outputs.

The NEMO model:

In the next year, a global 1/36° (ORCA36) multiyear hindcast will be produced, with NEMO 4.2. It will be forced by the ECMWF IFS 1 hour date set. Two twin hindcasts will be produced (without and with explicit tidal forcing). New NEMO 4.2 HPC features will be tested to improve the NEMO 4.2-ORCA36 performances.

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6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No changes have been made regarding the production-mode simulations, the ocean-only simulations, and the coupling infrastructure. While the improvements of the I/O in form of a switch to XIOS model output in the OpenIFS model have been realised for EC-Earth, the work on the ensemble I/O has been delayed and will be reported in the next deliverable D1.3.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

This deliverable is at the heart of the European strategy for HPC as it develops not only the software infrastructure that is required to run operational weather and climate models on (pre-)exascale supercomputers, but also specific applications that can use the scale of these machines that will soon be available within Europe. The tests and the comparison between the different models generate synergies between the modelling centres and helps to identify challenges and bottlenecks for the operational use of these computing resources. The results of this work package will feed directly into several upcoming EU projects (see next section).

8. Sustainability

The production mode simulations of ESIWACE2 will feed directly into the development of the Digital Twins of the Earth as part of the Destination Earth project which are based on operational, global, coupled simulations at unprecedented resolution for both weather and climate. They also prepare for the simulations of the NextGems project (30-year-long integration with IFS and ICON at storm-resolving resolution), and future developments in the WarmWorld project in Germany. Furthermore, the model configurations of ICON and IFS are identical to the configurations that are used for the DYAMOND model intercomparison project, which is also supported by WP1 of ESIWACE2.

The IFS model is used for operational weather predictions and improvements in model efficiency and scalability will benefit all ECMWF member and co-operating states or users of ECMWF weather predictions. The EC-Earth model will be used for climate model simulations and are in preparation for the next Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and improvements in scalability and performance will benefit the entire EC-Earth community.

NEMO is used as an ocean-only model but also as an ocean component of several coupled model configurations (including the DYNAMICO, IFS and EC-Earth). The possibility to run high-resolution 1/36 degree simulations with the NEMO model will therefore benefit a number of modelling groups and applications in both weather and climate prediction.

ICON is used as the production model of the German Weather service, and in a multitude of international weather and climate research projects. Improvements to the model will directly benefit the weather forecasts of the national weather services participating in the COSMO consortium (Germany, Switzerland, Italy, Greece, Poland, Romania, Russia, Israel)¹¹, as well as a rich scientific research community, including projects such as the H2020 project NextGEMS.

¹¹ <https://www.cosmo-model.org/>

The high-resolution developments will also inform and contribute to the WCRP Lighthouse Activity on Digital Earth.

While the production model simulations are directly benefiting from the developments in WP2 – in particular regarding the developments of DSLs and concurrent integrations of model components – the production runs of Work Package 1 will serve as reference for the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) of WP4 and the visualisation of WP5. For the latter, in particular the simulations of the DYAMOND model intercomparison are important.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The results are presented to the scientific audience in terms of papers and presentation. The results of large-scale model demonstrators and the production-mode simulations of ESIWACE (phase 1 of ESIWACE and ESIWACE2) have also formed the basis for a number of large funding proposals. To further enhance the dissemination of results and development in high-resolution simulations for weather and climate predictions, sessions and EGU and mini-symposia at PASC have been organised.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Workshop	The new very-high-resolution EC-Earth 4 climate demonstrator	21/09/2021 - 19th Workshop on high performance computing in meteorology (virtual)	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/5534659	100
Workshop	Talk	24/11/2020 - Presentation by Peter Dueben at the ORAP User Forum	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/4412151#.X_GP2jRxd_aQ	30
Workshop	Talk	28/09/2020 - Presentation by Peter	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/	50

		Dueben at the Multi-Core 2020 meeting		record/4412177#.X_GV9DRxdaQ	
Session organisation	Convening of a session on "High resolution modelling of weather and climate"	On 19/04/2021 at the virtual EGU GA 2021	Scientific		100
Workshop	Talk	28/06/2021 - Seminar talk by Peter Dueben at Oak Ridge National Laboratory	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/5152016#.YQbv8bris2w	80
Workshop	Talk	25/05/2021 - Seminar talk by Peter Dueben at the NCI TechTake seminar series	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/5152044#.YQb2ubris2w	80
Workshop	Talk	01/10/2021 - CLIVAR/Ocean Model Development Panel: Future Directions in Basin and Global High-resolution Ocean Modelling	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/5571815	100
Participation to a conference	Talk	29/05/2021 - vPICO Presentation by Julia Duras at the virtuell EGU 2021	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/5713428	140
Participation to a conference	Poster	29/05/2021 - vPICO extra material by Julia Duras at the virtuell EGU 2021	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/record/5713492	140

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <u>open access</u> be provided to this publication?
Submitted	Evaluation and optimisation of the I/O scalability for the next generation of Earth system models: IFS CY43R3 and XIOS 2.0 integration as a case study	Yepes-Arbós, X., van den Oord, G., Acosta, M. C., and Carver, G. D	Geoscientific Model Development	Yes
Published	Resilience and fault-tolerance in high-performance computing for numerical weather and climate prediction	Benacchio, Bonaventura, Altenbernd, Cantwell, Dueben, Gillard, Giraud, Góddeke, Raffin, Teranishi, Wedi	International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications	Yes
Published	Number Formats, Error Mitigation, and Scope for 16-Bit Arithmetics in Weather and Climate Modeling Analyzed With a Shallow Water Model	Kloewer, Dueben, Palmer	JAMES	Yes
Published	Model intercomparison of COSMO 5.0 and IFS 45r1 at kilometer-scale grid spacing	Zeman, Wedi, Dueben, Ban, Schaer	Geoscientific Model Development	Yes
Published	A Comparison of Data-Driven Approaches to Build Low-Dimensional Ocean Models	Agarwal, Kondrashov, Dueben, Ryzhov, Berloff	JAMES	Yes
Published	Compressing atmospheric data into its real information content	Kloewer, Razinger, Dominguez, Dueben, Palmer	Nature Computational Science	Yes

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A